

REFINEMENT OF CYCLIC R-CURVE DETERMINATION ON EXTRINSICALLY SHORT CRACKS BY ANNEALING

L. Walch^{1*}, T. Klünsner¹, G. Ressel¹, A. Hohenwarter² & R. Pippan³

Reliable information on the resistance to fatigue crack propagation is a key parameter for fatigue life predictions. However, an accurate determination of the cyclic R-curve is demanding. One challenge in the involved experimental techniques consists of introducing a pre-crack. When pre-cracks are generated by cyclic compression-compression loading, a zone of tensile residual stresses of up to material yield strength is generated ahead of the crack tip. A small zone of these residual stresses remains even when the sample is subjected to very high numbers of load cycles during pre-cracking. These stresses may affect crack propagation during the actual crack propagation test and should consequently be removed. However, subsequent stress-relief annealing is impractical for numerous metallic material classes due to undesired microstructural alterations at the temperatures required for stress relief. In the present contribution, the above-described issue is addressed for a high speed steel using single-edge notched bending specimens pre-cracked at various stages of a typical high speed steel heat treatment process.

Keywords: Cyclic R-curve, fatigue crack propagation threshold, heat treatment, pre-cracking

INTRODUCTION

For most industrial applications, an accurate estimation of tool lifetimes is a necessity for resource-saving and cost-effective process flows. Considering conventional crack-growth diagrams, as first established by Paris, P. and Erdogan, F. [1], the largest fraction of total tool lifetime is spent in the region below the long crack threshold. Thus, precise and accurate knowledge of the threshold of stress intensity factor range for short cracks is paramount as summarized by Zerbst, U. et al. [2]. Achieving accurate estimations also requires good knowledge of the dependence of the short crack threshold as a function of crack extension, i.e. crack growth resistance, discussed in more detail by Maierhofer, J. et al. [3].

The increase of the threshold of stress intensity factor range for crack propagation with crack extension to the plateau of the long crack threshold of stress intensity factor range is usually referred to as R-curve behavior, depicted in cyclic R-curves [3]. Reliably and accurately determining these cyclic R-curves demands appropriate specimen preparation, testing and crack growth measurement techniques. Typically, specimen preparation for threshold tests includes the initiation of a pre-crack via pre-cracking in compression-compression loading as proposed by Pippan, R. [4]. The generation of cracks under compression-compression loading has been reported somewhat earlier by Suresh, S. [5], Christman, T. and Suresh, S. [6], and Pippan, R. [7]. This pre-cracking technique for threshold measurements has seen widespread use over recent decades, e.g. Pippan, R. et al. [8], Newman Jr., J. et al. [9], Jesner, G. and

¹ Materials Center Leoben Forschung GmbH (MCL), Roseggerstraße 12, A-8700, Leoben, Austria

² Department of Materials Science, Chair of Materials Physics, Montanuniversity Leoben, Jahnstraße 12, A-8700 Leoben, Austria

³ Erich Schmid Institute of Materials Science, Austrian Academy of Sciences, A-8700 Leoben, Austria

Pippan, R. [10], and Lintner, A. et al. [11]. Pre-cracking in compression-compression loading to determine long crack thresholds of stress intensity factor range thresholds is consequently considered a well-established preparation technique, see e.g. Pippan, R. et al. [12] and has been recently included in the ASTM procedure for fatigue crack growth measurement.

However, several pre-cracking parameters such as pre-crack length, pre-cracking load ratio and others influence subsequent crack growth during testing and hence cyclic R-curve behavior, as documented by Tabernig, B. and Pippan, R. [13]. These influences necessitate great care in parameter selection and conduct during pre-cracking. Still, significant tensile residual stresses likely remain ahead of the pre-crack tip due to the limitations of stress-relief by pre-cracking [13]. The cyclic R-curves determined on such samples hence exhibit an initial shift to higher crack extension rates, i.e. to a reduced initial slope of the cyclic R-curve compared to a tensile residual stress-free case. Another issue is the experimental scatter due to pre-cracking-dependent variations in tensile residual stress magnitudes ahead of the crack tips that reduce the reproducibility of determined cyclic R-curves, as observed for varying load amplitudes at the point of pre-crack initiation [13]. All these phenomena are more pronounced in high-strength materials, such as high speed steels or hardmetals, which usually exhibit a steep initial slope of the cyclic R-curve. To address this issue, James, M. N. et al. [14] added additional tensile-tensile loading after pre-cracking in compression-compression loading for hardmetal specimens to alleviate tensile residual stresses introduced during pre-cracking.

Nonetheless, adding compressive residual stresses to counter tensile residual stress bears its own risks and relies on exact conduct in two different pre-cracking setups. In contrast, stress-relief annealing is an effective, yet simple procedure to remove residual stresses. Due to the microstructural changes associated with the temperatures required for full stress relief, adding such a heat treatment after pre-cracking is usually not feasible. Still, the manufacturing routes of a wide variety of materials include one or several heat treatment steps in a fitting temperature range. For example, the heat treatment process for high speed steels after tool or specimen shaping typically includes one hardening and up to three tempering steps with applied temperatures usually above 500 °C. Combining specimen preparation with the heat treatment process consequently offers an opportunity to diminish or remove tensile residual stresses by utilizing necessary heat treatment steps also for stress-relief annealing. To the best of the authors' knowledge this concept has to date not been tested.

The present work aims to study this novel concept with regard to resource-efficient refinement of an established experimental technique for cyclic R-curve determination. Specimens with identical full heat treatments had pre-cracks introduced at various stages of the heat treatment process and were then fatigued under identical conditions. The crack extensions were measured via a direct-current potential-drop (DCPD) technique and compared with fractographs recorded using a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

All specimens examined in this study were manufactured from the same batch of a commercially available high speed steel grade traded as S390 Microclean™ by voestalpine BÖHLER Edelstahl GmbH & Co KG [15]. All tests were performed under ambient air conditions at temperatures ranging from 25 °C to 35 °C. The nominal chemical composition of the used steel grade is given in TABLE 1. The material was received in a soft-annealed state.

TABLE 1: Nominal chemical composition in weight percent (wt.%) of the high speed steel grade S390 Microclean™.

Fe	C	W	Mo	V	Co	Cr	Si	Mn	
68.54	1.64	10.40	2.00	4.80	8.00	4.80	0.60	0.30	wt.%

The heat treatment was identical for all investigated specimens. The specimens were quenched and tempered to a composite Rockwell C hardness of 66 HRC. The austenitization temperature was 1150 °C in a vacuum with a three minute holding time, followed by quenching under nitrogen (5 bar) to room temperature. Specimens were tempered three times for two hours at 560 °C in air. The specimens differed only as to at which heat treatment stage the pre-crack was introduced. The preparation schemes are illustrated in FIGURE 1, in which the full heat treatment and the heat treatment stages at which the specimens were pre-cracked are shown. Specimens were either pre-cracked in I: soft-annealed, II: as-quenched, III: quenched and 2x2h-tempered, or IV: 3x2h-tempered, the conventional, fully heat-treated state. If pre-cracked prior to heat treatment completion, the subsequent heat treatment step or steps were performed afterwards. The insertion of the pre-cracking procedure during the heat treatment process enabled the applied heat treatments to act as stress-relief annealing for the tensile residual stresses ahead of the pre-crack tips.

FIGURE 1: Heat treatment procedure for all specimens with the stages at which pre-cracking was done annotated accordingly.

The crack growth tests were performed using fully heat-treated single edge notched bend (SENB) specimens as shown in FIGURE 2 a) with a total length of 110 mm, a height of 20 mm, and a width of 6 mm. Notches were made at the axial center of a the 110 mm x 6 mm plane by electrical discharge machining (EDM), with a depth of 4 mm and a width of 0.3 mm. Specimen preparation was performed as described in [13]. First, the notches were sharpened by a razor blade in combination with 1 μm diamond polishing suspension moved along the EDM notch base, perpendicular to the specimen's long axis. Razor blades were exchanged after each specimen to avoid uneven wear along their edges. Second, specimens were pre-cracked in uniaxial compression-compression loading under a stress ratio of $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} =$

10. Specimens that were pre-cracked before their final heat treatment step were then heat treated to the same material state as specimens pre-cracked in state IV: 3x2h-tempered.

To introduce pre-cracks, the initially applied stress intensity factor range ΔK_{start} , defined as $K_{max} - K_{min}$, was set at a level at which, from prior experience with the material, no crack initiation was expected, and then increased with a step size of $1 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ using the following procedure: The specimens were loaded with $\Delta K_{start} = 20 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, when in soft-annealed state (I), and with $40 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the other investigated specimen pre-cracking states (II, III, IV) for 20,000 load cycles, respectively. Then, the specimen's notch base region was inspected using light optical microscopy (LOM) to determine whether a crack had initiated. If this was the case, the pre-crack length was measured. If no crack was detected, the stress intensity factor range ΔK was increased by $1 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ and the procedure then repeated. Upon optical detection of a pre-crack, the respective applied level of stress intensity factor range ΔK_{end} was documented, see TABLE 2. The initiated pre-crack length in specimens pre-cracked in states I-III were measured and documented using LOM before and after the subsequent heat treatment step or steps. A detailed overview of the pre-cracking conditions for all presented specimens is included in TABLE 2.

To test whether or not an oxide layer formed on the pre-crack surface during heat treatment performed after pre-cracking had any significant effect on the fatigue crack propagation during $R = -1$ loading, the specimen III-C was overloaded prior to $R = -1$ testing. The overloading to -1.95 kN (± 0.08) corresponding to an applied stress intensity factor K_{min} of $-6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (± 0.25) was applied after the specimen was pre-cracked and then fully heat-treated, before the start of the crack propagation test. Note that the specimens' pre-crack surface state was identical to that of the other specimens pre-cracked prior to the final heat treatment step or steps. However, due to the overload, significant tensile residual stresses were introduced ahead of the pre-crack tip.

TABLE 2: Pre-cracking parameters with respective stress intensity factor range ΔK_{end} of first pre-crack detection after 20,000 load cycles N applied to SENB specimens at a certain stage within the heat treatment of the investigated specimens. The associated pre-crack lengths measured before and after final heat treatment are also included. The estimated uncertainty range for given pre-crack lengths is 5% (with long pre-cracks) to 20% (with short pre-cracks) of the total crack length. The estimated plastic zone extent r_p calculated using Equation (1) is included in the rightmost column for material states with known yield strengths.

Specimen	Pre-cracking conditions			Pre heat treatment	Post heat treatment	Plastic zone size
	ΔK_{end} [MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$]	N [-]	Specimen state [-]	Δa [μm]	Δa [μm]	r_p [μm]
I-A	25	20,000	I: soft-annealed	104	97	-
I-B	30	20,000	I: soft-annealed	173	171	-
II-A	55	20,000	II: as-quenched	8	10	-
II-B	50	20,000	II: as-quenched	23	25	-
III-A	48	20,000	III: 2x2h-tempered	15	16	115
III-B	52	20,000	III: 2x2h-tempered	32	29	136
III-C	47	20,000	III: 2x2h-tempered	21	18	111
IV-A	55	20,000	IV: 3x2h-tempered	-	35	152
IV-B	45	20,000	IV: 3x2h-tempered	-	14	102

The crack growth tests were performed for all specimens in an eight-point bending test setup at room temperature with a stress ratio of $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} = -1$. The applied stress intensity factor range ΔK was always $5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, which is slightly below the expected long crack threshold of stress intensity factor range ΔK_{th} of $6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ as observed by Jesner, G. [17] for the specimen material state and the applied stress ratio considered in the current work. Loads were applied with a frequency of 40 Hz until no crack propagation smaller than the detection limit of LOM of approximately $\pm 3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ was observed for about 100,000 load cycles. The aforementioned crack propagation was measured via a direct-current potential-drop (DCPD) setup, shown in FIGURE 2 c) and d). Crack propagations observed via changes in potential were correlated with crack lengths determined from fractographs attained by SEM. Since the cracks stopped propagating before fracture, the specimens were afterwards fractured in a three-point-bending setup prior to SEM imaging of the fracture faces.

FIGURE 2: Test setup used to fatigue the SENB specimens. a) Used specimen geometry. b) SEM image in secondary electron contrast mode for the pre-crack of specimen I-B after full heat treatment. c) Test setup with current I and voltage U contacts placed as indicated. d) Vectors of load application are schematically included for the compressive load situation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reproducibility of crack growth tests on specimen pre-cracked in the states I-IV was tested by ensuring that at least two identical tests were performed for each presented specimen state. The observed results are presented and discussed in the following.

Crack behavior during heat treatment

The relevant pre-crack lengths before and after performing the heat treatments are included in TABLE 2. Note that for no specimen the exact same pre-crack lengths before and after heat

treatment were observed. This is connected with the limited resolution of LOM. The associated pre-crack lengths were determined with a resolution uncertainty range that was estimated from smallest to largest relative deviation of observed pre-crack lengths in the range of 5 – 20 % of the total measured crack length. Furthermore, measurements in the μm -regime on the same pre-crack differed by some margin even with the same performing operator and without interim heat treatments. Thus, situational replicability pre-, and post-heat treatment is limited. For these reasons no definitive statement can be made on changes of pre-crack length due to heat treatment. However, in the authors opinion the found differences can be attributed to limitations of resolution in LOM and measurement precision and not to physical changes in pre-crack length due to the applied heat treatments.

Oxidation of the pre-cracks during heat treatment must be assumed given the ambient air atmosphere and used temperatures. However, work by Maierhofer, J. et al. [18] showed that during fatigue tests performed in ambient air, oxide layers form even at room temperature. Moreover, the main effect on fatigue crack propagation kinetics was that of abraded oxide particles that either accumulated at or were transported away from the crack tip. Since such oxide particles are generated by continuously forming and abraded oxide layers on a crack surface it is reasonable to assume that the influence of an oxide layer formed before the start of the $R = -1$ fatigue test on its outcome, whether at room or elevated temperature, be minimal. The SEM image of the pre-crack of specimen I-B after full heat treatment shown in FIGURE 2 b) also shows neither discernible crack closure due to oxidation, nor any detectable crack tip blunting.

Effect of pre-cracking before annealing on crack propagation

As mentioned previously, all crack growth tests were performed using a stress ratio of $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} = -1$ at a stress intensity factor range ΔK of $5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, slightly below the long crack threshold of stress intensity factor range ΔK_{th} [17]. These loading conditions were chosen to ensure an experimentally measurable subcritical crack extension above the short crack threshold of stress intensity factor range. The crack extensions were derived from the measured change of the potential-drop following Johnson H. H. [19], applying the direct-current potential-drop (DCPD)-technique as described e.g. by Merah, N. [20]. The results for specimens pre-cracked in states I: soft-annealed, II: as-quenched, III: 2x2h-tempered, and IV: 3x2h-tempered, the conventional, fully heat-treated state are shown in FIGURE 3. The presented results show the following trends: Firstly, a considerable reduction in total crack extension relative to conventionally pre-cracked specimens was found in stress-relieved specimens. Secondly, all stress-relieved specimens exhibit a comparable crack extension.

FIGURE 3: Development of crack extension Δa plotted against applied load cycles N for specimens pre-cracked at different stages of the heat treatment process. Note the difference in crack extension in specimens pre-cracked conventionally after full heat treatment compared to specimens pre-cracked before the final heat treatment step.

The fatigue cracks' length examined after final fracture exhibited similar trends. Representative SEM fractographs of the fatigue cracks after final fracture of the samples are presented in FIGURE 4. In all cases the mid-section of the fracture surface was investigated in order to characterize an area subjected to plane strain conditions. The crack extensions for specimens pre-cracked in states I-III were in the range of 1-10 μm , whereas 20-40 μm long fatigue cracks were observed in conventionally prepared specimens that were pre-cracked after full heat treatment (in state IV).

The level of total crack extension in the stress-relieved specimen III-C that was overloaded after heat treatment was similar to that of specimens pre-cracked conventionally in state IV. This behavior is a strong indication that the tensile residual stress relief is the main cause for the observed significant differences in total crack extension during fatigue testing. As a consequence, oxide layers formed on pre-crack surfaces during heat treatment did not detectably affect total crack extensions. Consequently, at least the first point of the crack extension of an R-curve determined for a conventionally pre-cracked high-strength material is significantly overestimated. Hence, such R-curves then do not reflect material response but pre-cracking conditions.”

FIGURE 4: Secondary electron contrast mode SEM micrographs of the crack faces close to the notches' lateral center, where plane strain conditions during loading can be assumed. a)-d) Fracture faces of the following specimens are shown: I-B, II-A, III-A, IV-B.

In the literature (see [5], Holm, D. K. et al. [21], [7]) the maximum possible length of pre-cracks at the point of crack arrest is usually related to the extent of the monotonic plastic zone r_p established upon application of the initial load during pre-cracking. This assumption was also made in the present work. The relation used to calculate r_p is given in Equation (1), in which $|K_{max}|$ represents the maximum absolute value of the applied stress intensity factor and $R_{p0.2}$ the yield strength for the material state of the specimens [5,21]. [16] determined a yield strength of roughly 2800 MPa for the high speed steel grade S390 Microclean tempered three times for two hours at 550 °C, which was assumed as a sufficiently comparable state for the here-discussed material that was pre-cracked in states III (2x2h-tempered) and IV (3x2h-tempered).

$$r_p = \frac{1}{\pi} * \left(\frac{|K_{max}|}{R_{p0.2}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Applying Equation (1) to the stress intensity factor ranges given in TABLE 2 for the pre-cracking of specimens IV-A and -B with the above-presented yield strength results in estimated maximum pre-crack lengths in the range of 100 μm and 150 μm for ΔK_{end} of 45 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ and 55 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ respectively. In the literature, a typical ratio of pre-crack extension at point of pre-crack arrest, i.e. the pre-crack saturation length, and estimated plastic zone size in the range of two to three has been reported [21]. For the pre-crack lengths and estimated plastic zone sizes presented in TABLE 2 this ratio is in the range of four to six. Since the observed ratio is higher than reported in literature, the pre-cracks had not necessarily grown to saturation length in the monotonic plastic zone at the end of pre-cracking. However, the difference of observed pre-crack length to saturation length is likely in the range of 3-7 μm , at which point the length ratio reported in literature would be observed. Hence, the differences in fatigue crack lengths of conventionally and stress-relieved specimens propagated using the described eight-point bending test setup were likely due to significant tensile residual stress fields remaining from pre-cracking. Assuming the estimated difference between observed pre-crack and saturation lengths is correct, longer pre-cracking would not alleviate these tensile residual stresses and similar results would be obtained on specimens pre-cracked using more load cycles. Still, it is recommended by the authors to test this assumption by pre-cracking a fully heat treated specimen for at least 80,000 load cycles as suggested in [5,21] and then subject this specimen to identical testing conditions as presented in the current work.

To summarize the observations described above, incorporating the pre-cracking procedure into the heat treatment process resulted in reduced total crack extension compared to conventionally prepared specimens pre-cracked after the heat treatment. In contrast, if the pre-cracking was followed by another heat treatment step, the position of the stage at which the pre-cracking was performed within the heat treatment sequence did not influence total crack extension.

CONCLUSION

Integrating the pre-cracking of fatigue specimens made of high speed steel into the heat treatment process for stress-relief annealing is a simple method to remove tensile residual stresses ahead of the pre-crack tip retained from preparation of single-edge notched bend (SENB) specimens. The here-presented technique allows for refined crack growth characterization at stress intensity ranges below the long crack threshold of stress intensity factor range with minimal added logistical effort. Two main conclusions are drawn from the current work that are summarized in the following:

1. Introducing a pre-crack into specimens that require further heat treatment enables the use of the conventional heat treatment route for stress-relief annealing. If available, the usage of a vacuum oven is recommended to limit oxidation of the crack faces.
2. If pre-cracks are introduced prior to the final heat treatment step, the position of this step within the heat treatment sequence does not noticeably influence crack growth in subsequent crack growth tests. However, this does not preclude the occurrence of influences smaller than the detection limit of the here-applied measurement techniques.
3. Stress relieved specimens compressively overloaded after heat treatment exhibit similar behavior as specimens pre-cracked after full heat treatment. This indicates that the tensile residual stress relief is the main cause of reduced total crack extension during fatigue testing.

REFERENCE LIST

- [1] Paris, P. and Erdogan, F. *Journal of Basic Engineering*, 1963, pp. 528–533.
- [2] Zerbst, U. et al. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.153, 2016, pp. 190–243.
- [3] Maierhofer, J. et al. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.198, 2018, pp. 45–64.
- [4] Pippan, R. *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Fatigue and Fatigue Thresholds*, Vol.2, 1987, pp. 932–938.
- [5] Suresh, S. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.21, No. 3, 1985, pp. 453–463.
- [6] Christman, T. and Suresh, S. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.23, No. 6, 1986, pp. 953–964.
- [7] Pippan, R. *Fatigue Fract Engng Mater Struct*, Vol.9, No. 5, 1987, pp. 319–328.
- [8] Pippan, R. et al. *Journal of Testing and Evaluation; (United States)*, 22:2, 1994.
- [9] Newman Jr., J. et al. *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol.27, No. 10-12, 2005, pp. 1432–1440.
- [10] Jesner, G. and Pippan, R. *Metall Mater Trans A*, Vol.40, No. 4, 2009, pp. 810–817.
- [11] Lintner, A. et al. *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol.163, 2022, pp. 107083.
- [12] Pippan, R. et al. *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol.16, 1994, pp. 579–582.
- [13] Tabernig, B. and Pippan, R. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.69, 2002, pp. 899–907.
- [14] James, M. N. et al. *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol.25, 1990, pp. 4810–4814.

- [15] voestalpine BÖHLER Edelstahl GmbH & Co KG, 2022, S390 MICROCLEAN - BÖHLER Edelstahl GmbH & Co KG. <https://www.boehler-edelstahl.com/de/products/s390/>. Accessed 4 April 2023.
- [16] Marsoner, S. Phd-Thesis, *Gefügeeinfluss auf statische und zyklische Eigenschaften von PM-Werkzeugstahl*, Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, 2002.
- [17] Jesner, G. Phd-Thesis, *Ermüdungsverhalten von hochfesten PM-Werkzeugstählen*, Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, 2007.
- [18] Maierhofer, J. et al. *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol.117, 2018, pp. 21–26.
- [19] Johnson H. H. *Materials Research & Standards*, Vol.5, 1965, pp. 442–445.
- [20] Merah, N. *Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering*, Vol.9, No. 2, 2003, pp. 160–175.
- [21] Holm, D. K. et al. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol.23, No. 6, 1986, pp. 1097–1106.